

The Determinants of Second Job Holding in Lithuania: A VECM Analysis

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[Abstract]

This paper aims to reveal the influence of hours constraint, interest rate and unemployment on second job holding in Lithuania using quarterly data from Eurostat for the period of 2005 Q1 to 2013 Q4. Application of ADF and PP tests show that all the variables are $I(1)$. The existence of two cointegrating equations is confirmed by the Johansen Trace and Maximum Eigenvalue tests. The FMOLS estimates of the cointegration relationship suggest that likelihood of second job holding decreases due to hours constraint, interest rate and unemployment rate in the long run. The error correction coefficient in the VECM analysis is found to be significant and negative. This finding confirms that there is a long run causality running from hours constraint, interest rate and unemployment to second job holding in Lithuania. But no short-run causality from hours constraint and unemployment to second job holding has been confirmed. The VECM Granger Causality Test demonstrates that except interest rate, the hours constraint and unemployment rate do not Granger cause second job holding in Lithuania.

Keywords: *Second Job Holding, Hours Constraint, Unemployment, FMOLS, VECM, Lithuania*

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Introduction

Second job holding (or moonlighting) is a major characteristic of the employment markets in almost all economies (Shisko and Rostker (1976), Krishnan (1990), Renna and Oaxaca (2006), Combos, McKay and Wright (2007), Husain (2014), Yamb and Bikoue (2016), Pouliakas (2017)). The flexible working conditions in contemporary economies have led to an increase in the number of people taking up second jobs in addition to their primary jobs (Baines and Newell (2004), Combos, McKay and Wright (2007), Ashwini, Mirthula and Preetha (2017)). In today's world, although very much common, the impact of second job holding is usually unclear. According to Casacuberta and Gandelman (2006), society benefits from the creation of value when an employee also works as a part-time artist. Multiple jobholding may also be welcomed if it is able to assist in acquiring certain abilities or if it serves as a catalyst for the development of new skills and acts as an ingredient of the occupational transition process (Dickey, Watson and Zangelidis (2009), Panos, Pouliakas and Zangelidis (2011)). Second job holding may also act as a strategy for lowering financial risk of the self-employed persons (ILO (2004)). However, the tendency to avoid paying income taxes on income from second jobs contributes to the shadow and underground economies (Frey and Schneider (2000), Schneider (2010), Barth and Ognedal (2005)). According to Biglaiser and

Ma (2007), inefficiencies in performance and productivity may also result in labour markets with both public and private provisions due to second jobholding. Faculty members' ability to teach may be impacted by their second jobs (Akande, Akindele, and Ologunde (2013)).

Employment levels might potentially be impacted by second jobholding (Bell, Hart and Wright (1997), Panos, Pouliakas and Zangelidis (2011), Hirsch, Husain and Winters (2015)). Therefore, the economics of second jobholding is a challenging field to study because of its contradictory effects on the economy. This paper is intended to investigate the long-run factors that contribute to second jobholding in Lithuania in terms of Johansen cointegration analysis using the quarterly data from Eurostat for the period of 2005 Q1 to 2013 Q4.

The Baltic nation of Lithuania became the first to declare its independence after being controlled by the former Soviet Union. Lithuania reclaimed her independence on 11th March 1990, when the Lithuanian Constituent Assembly approved the Act of the Re-Establishment of the State of Lithuania. The country joined the WTO on 31st May 2001 and it has been part of NATO since 29 March 2004. Lithuania became a full-fledged member of the European Union on 1st May 2004 and later adopted the European Union's single currency. Lithuania has had strong democratic traditions ever since gaining independence. With the implementation of several liberal reforms, Lithuania swiftly transitioned from a centrally planned to a market economy. The privatization of state-owned assets was one of Lithuania's most significant changes. Early in the 1990s, monetary reform was implemented in an effort to increase economic stability.

There has been a significant change in the Lithuanian economy from one centered on agriculture to one centered on services. With the largest economy and the fastest growth rates among the three Baltic countries, Lithuania is sometimes referred to as the 'Baltic Tiger'. The World Bank has categorized Lithuanian economy as a high-income economy. However, 2009 saw a terrible recession in Lithuania, as it did in other countries in East Europe. Following its economic recovery in 2010, the nation became one of the fastest growing economies in the European Union. Like any other economy, the Lithuanian economy is not immune to the prevalence of second job holding. Data from Eurostat indicate that in the first quarter of 2002, around 7% of working adults decided to take on a second job in order to sustain themselves. The prevalence of second jobholding declined to approximately 5% in the first quarter of 2015.

This study contributes to the literature in terms of identifying the long-run factors of second job holding in Lithuania by employing a vector error-correction (VECM) analysis. Following the introduction in Section 1, this paper is structured as follows: a review of some selected literature is covered in Section 2, the data, methodology, and model specification are covered in Section 3, the empirical results are presented in Section 4, and the study is concluded in Section 5.

Literature Review

Despite being common in almost all economies, there is little research on the economics of second job holding. The reasons behind second jobholding and its effects on the economy are two main traits that are examined in the literature. Most of the research has focused on cross-sectional or panel data analysis to identify the factors influencing the incidence of second job holding (Godager and Luras (2009), Adhikary and Pal (2012), Pal (2016)).

Research in second jobholding identified numerous economic and non-economic factors that are influencing workers' decision to hold second jobs. The most important factor of second jobholding is the 'hours constraint'. It is the constraint faced by an employee in supplying utility-maximizing hours of work in the primary job with a given (existing) wage rate. Shisko and Rostker (1976) has pioneered the concept of 'hours constraint' motive of multiple job holding using microeconomic theory of labour-leisure choice. Two counteracting forces influence the choice of labour supply when wage rate increases. Due to income effect, if leisure is seen to be normal good, increase in wage rate influence the workers to consume more leisure and work less hours. In contrast, due to substitution effect, increase in wage rate influence the workers to supply more working hours and consume less leisure. Equilibrium working hours is determined by the interaction between these two balancing factors. If workers cannot supply as much working hour in primary job as required for equilibrium, they decide to put their unused time towards taking on a second job as long as the wage rate of the second job exceeds the reservation wage.

Shisko and Rostker (1976)'s theoretical framework yields two important points. First, working hours in a second job have a negative relationship with wage rate of primary job if leisure is not seen as an inferior good. This is regarded as the wage or income constraint, which states that low wage rate in the primary employment will stimulate workers to grip for additional job. Second, there is an inverse association between labour supply to subsidiary jobs and hours spent in the primary job when the wage rate in subsidiary jobs is lower than the wage rate in the prime job. This is the hours constraint hypothesis which implies that if an employee is unable to devote as many hours as he or she desires to the higher-paying primary job, he or she will wish to supply unutilized hours to a lower-paying secondary job.

With the Tobit technique, Shisko and Rostker (1976) had estimated the labour supply curve of second jobholding using cross-section data and found the significant role of wage and hours constraints in determining second jobholding in the U.S. The prospective investigations have validated the hours constraint motive of second job holding (e.g., Krishnan (1990), Allen (1998), Conway and Kimmel (1998), Averett (2001), Nadrei (2003), Böheim and Taylor (2004), Heineck (2009), Livanos and Zangelidis (2008), Adhikary and Pal (2012)).

Lilja (1991) extended the list of factors influencing second job holding by including job heterogeneity motive in addition to constraint motives and empirically tested the presence of this motive among male workers in Finland.

Conway and Kimmel (1998), broadened the concept job heterogeneity of Lilja (1991) by generalizing the utility function which is not separable in hours spent to primary and secondary occupations.

The theoretical foundation of Conway and Kimmel (1998) clearly integrated two independent motives for second jobholding, the hours constraint motive and the job heterogeneity motive. By estimating a disequilibrium model of second jobholding using maximum likelihood method, Conway and Kimmel (1998) have estimated a reduced form second jobholding participation equation using panel data from the SIPP (Survey of Income and Program Participation) for adult men and confirmed empirical support for both the motives of second jobholding. The job heterogeneity motive of second jobholding has been verified further in prospective research (e.g., Kimmel and Conway (2001), Boheim and Taylor (2004), Renna and Oaxaca (2006)).

Culler and Bazzoli (1985) highlighted the financial motivation for second jobholding. Abdukadir (1992) extended the list of variables influencing second job holding by incorporating liquidity constraint as a possible reason. He argued that purchasing consumables such as a house or a new automobile necessitates the usage of liquid assets. Low current income relative to educational qualification may act as a constraint in managing liquid funds for immediate purchasing of consumables. Using data from Florida Consumer Surveys, Abdukadir (1992) shown that the presence of a liquidity constraint enhances the likelihood of second jobholding. He pointed out that workers employed permanently in a public sector job are more likely to moonlight, as their main job may help them to find second jobs.

Boheim and Taylor (2004) investigated two additional motives for second job holding, the negative financial shocks and heightened primary job insecurity, in addition to the hours constraint and job heterogeneity. Their empirical findings revealed that likelihood of second jobholding in the UK increases as a result of a negative financial shock while the effect of job insecurity is ambiguous. The study prioritized the job heterogeneity motive of second jobholding over temporary factors like constraint motives. According to Guariglia and Kim (1999), income unpredictability (or volatility) is the primary factor for second jobholding in Russia and second jobholding may be considered as an index of self – assurance device against income volatility.

Paxson and Sicherman (1996) developed the job portfolio or job packaging model of second job holding and objected the tendency to consider only constraint motives. They hold the view that doing multiple jobs is nothing more than a portfolio selection of employment opportunities between low-income steady primary jobs and high-income volatile secondary jobs. Further, they developed a stochastic dynamic model in which decisions to entry in subsidiary jobs and changes in principal job are taken simultaneously.

The empirical findings of Livanos and Zangelidis (2008) concluded that second jobholding in Greece is not only a result of hours constraint, but also a result of hedge against job insecurity. Holding second job as a defense against potential unemployment was studied by Bell, Hart and Wright (1997). Their study offered the idea that second jobholding is a good way to hedge against prospective unemployment in the U.K. Overtime pay regulation

as a constraint motive of second job holding was studied by Friesen (2001). According to Schaffner and Cooper (1991), a self-employed person may choose to pursue subsidiary employment because the marginal return to labour on the primary job is declining.

Second job holding might be a reaction to perceived employment instability due to increasing unemployment. Second job holding is believed to be associated with unemployment. The direction of the association between second job holding and unemployment is uncertain and dependent on the relative strength of income and substitution effects of wage change. According to Coghill (1967), the association between second job holding and unemployment is dependent on labour market circumstances. In the study of Bell, Hart and Wright (1997), having a second job is viewed as a technique for guarding against probable unemployment. Frey and Schneider (2000) also found a relationship between unemployment and second job holding in their investigation. According to Amuedo-Dorantes and Kimmel (2005), the possibility of having a second job increases during expansionary times, particularly for women. Robinson (2009) claimed that recruiters may advocate second job holding to cope with the economic downturn since secondary employment are more flexible than standard full-time jobs. In addition to the hours constraint motive, Wu, Baimbridge, and Zhu (2009) studied multiple jobholding as a strategy (hedge) against unemployment. Hipple (2010) proposed a shaky link between second job keeping and local unemployment rates. Panos, Pouliakas and Zangelidis (2011) revealed that having a second job may increase the likelihood of self-employment. Zangelidis (2014) found a favourable association between second job holding and unemployment. Hirsch, Husain and Winters (2015) studied the association between second job holding and unemployment rates in the United States from 1998 to 2013.

The key factors of second job holding found in this review of selected literature are the hours constraint, liquidity constraint and the unemployment rate. The purpose of this study is to explore the influence of these key factors on second job holding in Lithuania using VECM analysis.

3

Data, Model and Methodology

To explore the long run determinants of second job holding in Lithuania, quarterly data from Eurostat for the period of 2005 Q1 to 2013 Q4 is used. The hours constraint is proxied by the Eurostat data on 'average number of actual weekly hours of work in main job' and is abbreviated as HRS. Interest rate is used to investigate the efficacy of liquidity constraint. The quarterly Eurostat data on money market rate of interest (three-month basis) is used as the liquidity constraint and it is abbreviated as INT. The Eurostat data on 'unemployment rate' is used to represent unemployment (UNEMP). The rate of Second Job Holding (abbreviated as SJH) is calculated in terms of percentage of SJH to the NEP $\left(SJH = \frac{SJH}{NEP} \times 100 \right)$ where SJH and NEP are the Eurostat data on 'number of employed persons having second job' and 'number of employed persons' respectively. All data sets are transformed into logarithmic form.

The econometric model to be investigated in this paper is as follows:

$$LSJH_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LHRSt + \beta_2 LINT_t + \beta_3 UNEMP_t + u_t \quad (1)$$

where L stands for the logarithmic transformation of the variables, t stands for time, β 's are the regression parameters, u is the random error term and assumed to be normally, identically, and independently distributed.

To explore the efficacy of constraint motives in determining second job holding in Lithuania, the first step involves with the examination of stationarity of the data since non-stationary dataset may produce spurious regressions (Granger and Newbold (1974)). We'll perform both Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and Phillips-Perron (PP) test to find out stationarity of the data. The tests are involved in assessing whether differenced non-stationary series move together with the same variable in the long run.

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test of the variable Y_t is testing the hypothesis $H_0: \delta = 1$ of the following regression equations using OLS:

$$\text{With intercept:} \quad \Delta Y_t = \alpha + \delta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m \gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

$$\text{With intercept and trend:} \quad \Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \delta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m \gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

where Δ is the first difference, ε_t is the white noise error term and i is the lag order to be selected on the basis of Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) or Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC). The Phillips-Perron (PP) test makes a non-parametric correction of higher order autocorrelation of the standard Dickey-Fuller test with non-parametrically modified test statistics. Following the determination of the order of integration using the ADF and PP tests, the next step is to investigate cointegration between variables.

If all variables are proven to be stationary at the same level, we will use the likelihood ratio test based on maximum eigenvalue and trace statistics of the stochastic matrix of the Johansen (1988) cointegration procedure. For n -variate process X_t , the VAR model with lag order p can be represented as

$$X_t = C\mu_t + A_1 X_{t-1} + A_2 X_{t-2} + \dots + A_p X_{t-p} + U_t \quad (4)$$

where $X_t' = (x_{1t}, x_{2t}, \dots, x_{kt})$, and A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p are $(k \times k)$ matrices, U_t is the k dimensional vector of unobservable errors with zero mean and variance-covariance matrix Σ , μ_t is the vector of deterministic term and C is its corresponding coefficient matrix.

For cointegrated X_t , the VAR model (4) can be transformed into a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) form through the Granger representation theorem and can have the following form.

$$\Delta X_t = C\mu_t + \Pi X_{t-1} + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \Gamma_k \Delta X_{t-k} + U_t \quad (5)$$

where Π is a coefficient matrix of cointegrating relationships and Γ is a coefficient matrix of the lags of differenced variables. If X_t is supposed to be $I(1)$, then ΔX_t is $I(0)$, as are ΔX_{t-k} , $\forall k = 1, 2, \dots, p-1$. And ΠX_{t-1} , which contains the cointegrating relations, is $I(0)$. If the rank of $\Pi = 0$, then there is no cointegration. If the rank of $\Pi = k$, Π is invertible and all the variables are $I(0)$. If $0 < \text{rank}(\Pi) = r < k$, then X_t is $I(1)$ with r linearly cointegrating vectors. Johansen and Juselius (1990) formulated two likelihood ratio (LR) tests for determining the $\text{rank}(\Pi)$ using estimated eigenvalues ($\hat{\lambda}_i$, such that $\hat{\lambda}_1 \geq \hat{\lambda}_2 \geq \dots \geq \hat{\lambda}_n$), the Trace test and the Maximum Eigenvalue test.

In case of the Trace test, for sample size T , the LR test statistic tests the hypotheses $H_0: r = r_0$ against $H_1: r > r_0$ using the following statistic

$$LR_{trace} \left(\frac{r}{n} \right) = -T \sum_{i=r_0+1}^n \ln(1 - \hat{\lambda}_i) \quad (6)$$

In case of Maximum Eigenvalue test, the LR test statistic tests the hypotheses $H_0: r = r_0$ against $H_1: r = (r_0 + 1)$ using the following statistic

$$LR_{max} \left(\frac{r}{n+1} \right) = -T \ln(1 - \hat{\lambda}_{r_0+1}) \quad (7)$$

Before performing the cointegration test, the appropriate lag length p must be determined via a VAR (p) model using initial data. Likelihood ratio (LR), final prediction error (FPE), Akaike information criterion (AIC), Schwarz information criterion (SC) and Hannan–Quinn information criterion (HQ) are utilized in this study to determine the number of optimal lags. If cointegration between variables is observed, the corresponding VECM will be estimated; otherwise, VAR will be applied. Cointegration, or common stochastic trend, among variables in the long run as well as short run deviations from the long run equilibrium can be analyzed through VECM. In this study, $X_t' = (LSJH_t, LHRSt, LINT_t, LUNEMP_t)$ and we'll proceed to estimate VECM using maximum likelihood estimator of Johansen (1995).

We should apply the VECM Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests in terms of Edgeworth expansion corrected Likelihood Ratio (LRE) and Rao F statistics to test the autocorrelation of residuals. We should employ White Heteroskedasticity under the framework of VECM to test heteroscedasticity. The Jarque-Bera normality test should be used for multivariate residual normality testing. To ensure the stability of the calculated VECM, we should confirm that all roots have modulus smaller than one and are lie inside the unit circle. Lastly, the Granger causality test will be performed within the framework of VECM after confirmation of cointegration relationship amongst the variables.

Cointegration, or common stochastic trend, among variables in the long run as well as the short run deviations from the long run equilibrium can be analyzed through a VECM. The relevant Error Correction Model (ECM) corresponding to (1) will be estimated after observing the cointegration between variables. The error correction model to be estimated is

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta LSJH_t = & b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n b_{1i} \Delta LSJH_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n b_{2i} \Delta LHRSt_{-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n b_{3i} \Delta LINT_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^n b_{4i} \Delta LUNEMP_{t-i} + \lambda ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where ECT is the error correction term. A negative and significant error correction coefficient will indicate a stable long-run relationship in a sense that any short-term disequilibrium between the independent variables and the dependent variable will be corrected in the long run. The error correction coefficient describes how quickly the model recovers from an external shock. As a result, in VECM, the error correction term should be negative to represent a move towards long run equilibrium.

For residual diagnostics, we'll apply the VECM Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests in terms of Edgeworth expansion corrected Likelihood Ratio (LRE) and Rao F statistics to test the autocorrelation of residuals, White Heteroskedasticity test to test heteroscedasticity and the Jarque-Bera normality test for multivariate residual normality. To ensure the stability of the calculated VECM, we should confirm that all roots have modulus smaller than one and are lie inside the unit circle. Lastly, the Granger causality test will be performed within the framework of VECM after confirmation of cointegration relationship amongst the variables.

4

Empirical Results

The quarterly data of Lithuania for the period of 2005 Q1 to 2013 Q4 on SJH, HRS, INT and UNEMP from Eurostat (European Union's official statistics portal <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/lfs/data/database>) are used in this study. Table – 1 presents the unit root tests of the variables. Both ADF and PP tests confirm that all the variables are non-stationary in levels but stationary in first differences. Therefore, all the variables are I(1) and we can apply Johansen method to detect the cointegration among variables.

Before applying the Johansen cointegration test to see if there is a long-run relationship between variables, we must first calculate the optimal lag length using a VAR model with initial data. Because this study uses quarterly data and the data set is not too large, only three lags are considered to run VAR model for selection of optimal lag length. The lag order selection criteria for standard VAR are presented in Table 2. Except FPE and AIC, the selection criteria confirm that appropriate lag length is one. Therefore, we have to apply Johansen cointegration test with lag length one to find out the cointegration between second job holding, hours constraint, interest rate and unemployment in Lithuania.

Table – 1: Unit Root Test

	ADF Test Statistic				Phillips Perron (PP) Test Statistic			
	Intercept		Trend and Intercept		Intercept		Trend and Intercept	
	Level	First Difference	Level	First Difference	Level	First Difference	Level	First Difference
LSJH	-2.3472	-7.1914**	-2.2828	-11.9813**	-1.0359	-7.1593**	-0.7923	-7.2066**
LHRS	-1.4906	-5.6473**	-2.3162	-6.4946**	-1.448	-5.3592**	-2.0687	-5.3146**
LINT	0.1601	-4.2023**	-1.0767	-4.6686**	0.5481	-4.2023**	-1.0767	-4.7124**
LUNEMP	-1.2377	-3.5961**	-1.9056	-3.5365*	-2.6788	-3.5961*	-3.4577	-3.5365*

Note: ** denotes rejection of the null hypothesis at 1% level of significance.

* denotes rejection of the null hypothesis at 5% level of significance.

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Table -2: Lag Selection Criteria

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria						
Endogenous variables: LSJH LHRS LINT LUNEMP						
Exogenous variables: C						
Sample: 2005Q1 2013Q4						
Included observations: 33						
Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	189.8851	NA	1.50e-10	-11.26576	-11.08437	-11.20473
1	300.5953	187.8719*	4.88e-13	-17.00577	-16.09880*	-16.70061*
2	317.9140	25.19084	4.73e-13*	-17.08570*	-15.45314	-16.53639
3	331.9329	16.99263	6.03e-13	-16.96563	-14.60750	-16.17219
* indicates lag order selected by the criterion						
LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)						
FPE: Final prediction error						
AIC: Akaike information criterion						
SC: Schwarz information criterion						
HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion						

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

The results of the Johansen Trace test are presented in Table – 3 and Maximum Eigenvalue Test are presented in Table – 4. At the 5% level of significance, both the Trace and Maximum Eigenvalue tests confirm the existence of two cointegrating equations. The results suggest that the variables LSJH, LHRS, LINT and LUNEMP are associated in the long run. Therefore, the hours constraint, the liquidity constraint and the unemployment rate can be regarded as the main determinants of second job holding in Lithuania. Because cointegration exists, the long-run relationship between variables is estimated by FMOLS (Fully Modified Least Squares). To identify the long run relationship, the equation (1) is estimated through FMOLS and the estimated long run beta coefficients, t-statistics and p values for the cointegrating relationship are presented in Table – 5.

Table – 3: Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.612402	68.35912	47.85613	0.0002
At most 1 *	0.510219	36.13439	29.79707	0.0081
At most 2	0.250788	11.86528	15.49471	0.1635
At most 3	0.058467	2.048364	3.841466	0.1524
Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Table – 4: Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.612402	32.22473	27.58434	0.0117
At most 1 *	0.510219	24.26911	21.13162	0.0175
At most 2	0.250788	9.816916	14.26460	0.2242
At most 3	0.058467	2.048364	3.841466	0.1524
Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Table – 5: The Cointegration Relationship

Dependent Variable: LSJH				
Method: Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS)				
Sample (adjusted): 2005Q2 2013Q4				
Included observations: 35 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LHRS	-9.140363	1.857657	-4.920371	0.0000
LINT	-0.034213	0.017960	-1.904963	0.0661
LUNEMP	-0.105779	0.010711	-9.875649	0.0000
C	15.49549	2.953096	5.247202	0.0000
R-squared	0.718457	Mean dependent var	0.746321	
Adjusted R-squared	0.691211	S.D. dependent var	0.051875	
S.E. of regression	0.028826	Sum squared resid	0.025759	
Long-run variance	0.000621			

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Table -5 confirms that hour constraint and the unemployment rate have a significant influence in predicting second job holding in Lithuania. The negative sign of the coefficient of LHRS implies that increased working hours in primary jobs lowers the prevalence of second jobs in Lithuania. This finding is consistent with the hours-constraint motive of second job holding. The negative sign of the coefficient of LUNEMP suggests that high unemployment rate reduces the likelihood of second job holding in Lithuania. The beta coefficient of LINT is significant at 6.6 percent and this is indicative that decreased money market interest rate has an inducement effect on second job holding in Lithuania.

As the cointegration vector exists, VECM (Vector Error Correction Model), a variant of restricted VAR (Vector Auto Regression), is the ideal model for analyzing short-run dynamics among variables. The results of VECM are presented in Table – 6. Since there are two cointegration equations, there are two error correction terms, the CointEq1 and the CointEq2. However, as we are only interested in the LSJH as the dependent variable, we simply evaluate the necessary error correction term CointEq1, which is negative and significant. Hence, there is a long run causality running from LHRS, LINT and LUNEMP to LSJH. The negative sign implies that a quarter's divergence from the long run equilibrium is compensated. In this study, the error correction term for LSJH is - 0.77, indicating that the departure from long-run equilibrium is corrected by 77% per quarter. Except the

coefficient of D(LINT(-1)), all the coefficients of D(LSJH(-1)), D(LHRS(-1)) and D(LUNEMP(-1)) are insignificant at 5% level of significance. As a result, there is no short-run causality from LHRS and LUNEMP to LSJH, but all the variables have long-run causality to LSJH.

Table – 6: Estimation of the VECM parameters: Short Run Dynamics

Sample (adjusted): 2005Q3 2013Q4				
Included observations: 34 after adjustments				
Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []				
Error Correction:	D(LSJH)	D(LHRS)	D(LINT)	D(LUNEMP)
CointEq1	-0.774616*** (0.26410) [-2.93305]	-0.018641 (0.01200) [-1.55392]	-1.869520*** (0.70999) [-2.63315]	0.718982 (0.84066) [0.85525]
CointEq2	-4.917465 (4.15834) [-1.18255]	-0.835915*** (0.18889) [-4.42546]	-10.30297 (11.1791) [-0.92162]	37.30280*** (13.2366) [2.81815]
D(LSJH(-1))	0.215015 (0.21722) [0.98984]	0.019892** (0.00987) [2.01595]	1.645787*** (0.58397) [2.81825]	-1.066554 (0.69145) [-1.54248]
D(LHRS(-1))	-3.991121 (4.00271) [-0.99710]	0.508911* (0.18182) [2.79901]	1.971751 (10.7608) [0.18324]	-14.93479 (12.7412) [-1.17216]
D(LINT(-1))	-0.129023** (0.05986) [-2.15537]	-0.001934 (0.00272) [-0.71125]	0.272613* (0.16093) [1.69399]	0.374877** (0.19055) [1.96737]
D(LUNEMP(-1))	-0.035946 (0.06802) [-0.52842]	0.007062*** (0.00309) [2.28561]	0.007515 (0.18287) [0.04109]	0.038573 (0.21653) [0.17814]
C	-0.002037 (0.00631) [-0.32303]	-0.000246 (0.00029) [-0.85813]	-0.019712 (0.01695) [-1.16264]	0.017736 (0.02008) [0.88346]
R-squared	0.378247	0.466866	0.340589	0.461716
Adj. R-squared	0.240079	0.348392	0.194053	0.342097
F-statistic	2.737595	3.940656	2.324273	3.859897
Prob(F-statistic)	0.032904	0.005878	0.061350	0.006567
Durbin-Watson stat	1.851617	1.970107	2.163878	1.997135

*** denotes significant at 1% level

** denotes significant at 5% level

* denotes significant at 10% level

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

The residual analysis for model diagnostic testing is presented in Table – 7. The White heteroscedasticity test reveals that there is no problem with heteroscedasticity in this VECM analysis since the probability value of White's Chi-square statistic is greater than 0.05. The Edgeworth expansion adjusted Likelihood Ratio (LRE) and Rao F statistics are used in the VECM Residual Serial Correlation LM Test. Since p values of all statistics (both LRE and Rao F) are greater than 0.05, no autocorrelation is confirmed in this VECM analysis.

Table - 7: Diagnostic Tests of the VECM

Diagnostic Tests	Results																																			
VEC Residual Heteroskedasticity Tests	Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity																																			
	White Heteroskedasticity Tests (No cross term): Chi-sq: 127.9858 df: 120 Prob. (Chi-sq): 0.2921																																			
VEC Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests	White Heteroskedasticity Tests (Including cross term): Chi-sq: 279.4797 df: 270 Prob. (Chi-sq): 0.3329																																			
	Sample: 2005Q1 2013Q4 Included observations: 34 Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at lag h																																			
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Lag</th> <th>LRE* stat</th> <th>df</th> <th>Prob.</th> <th>Rao F-stat</th> <th>df</th> <th>Prob.</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>14.89024</td> <td>16</td> <td>0.5327</td> <td>0.933309</td> <td>(16, 61.7)</td> <td>0.5371</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>16.78573</td> <td>16</td> <td>0.3996</td> <td>1.067287</td> <td>(16, 61.7)</td> <td>0.4044</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10.03568</td> <td>16</td> <td>0.8648</td> <td>0.606557</td> <td>(16, 61.7)</td> <td>0.8666</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>15.02836</td> <td>16</td> <td>0.5226</td> <td>0.942947</td> <td>(16, 61.7)</td> <td>0.5271</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Lag	LRE* stat	df	Prob.	Rao F-stat	df	Prob.	1	14.89024	16	0.5327	0.933309	(16, 61.7)	0.5371	2	16.78573	16	0.3996	1.067287	(16, 61.7)	0.4044	3	10.03568	16	0.8648	0.606557	(16, 61.7)	0.8666	4	15.02836	16	0.5226	0.942947	(16, 61.7)	0.5271
Lag	LRE* stat	df	Prob.	Rao F-stat	df	Prob.																														
1	14.89024	16	0.5327	0.933309	(16, 61.7)	0.5371																														
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4	15.02836	16	0.5226	0.942947	(16, 61.7)	0.5271																														
	Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at lags 1 to h																																			
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	*Edgeworth expansion corrected likelihood ratio statistic.																																			

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Table - 8: Normality and Stability Tests of the VECM

VEC Residual Normality Tests	Null Hypothesis: Residuals are multivariate normal																				
Orthogonalization: Cholesky (Lutkepohl)	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Component</th> <th>Jarque-Bera</th> <th>df</th> <th>Prob.</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0.397366</td> <td>2</td> <td>0.8198</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>0.616195</td> <td>2</td> <td>0.7348</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>2.666952</td> <td>2</td> <td>0.2636</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>1.068951</td> <td>2</td> <td>0.5860</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Component	Jarque-Bera	df	Prob.	1	0.397366	2	0.8198	2	0.616195	2	0.7348	3	2.666952	2	0.2636	4	1.068951	2	0.5860
	Component	Jarque-Bera	df	Prob.																	
1	0.397366	2	0.8198																		
2	0.616195	2	0.7348																		
3	2.666952	2	0.2636																		
4	1.068951	2	0.5860																		
	Joint 4.749464 8 0.7840																				
Stability Test: Inverse Roots of AR Characteristic Polynomial	<p>Inverse Roots of AR Characteristic Polynomial</p>																				

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

To check whether the residuals are white noise, the multivariate normality test with Cholesky (Lutkepohl) orthogonalization is conducted and presented in Table -8. Since the values of Jarque-Bera statistics are greater than 0.05, the normality of residuals at five percent level of significance is accepted. Further, as is evident in Table -8, the VECM model satisfies all stability conditions since all the roots lie inside the unit circle.

Table – 9: VECM Granger Causality Test

Block Exogeneity Wald Tests				
Sample: 2005Q1 2013Q4				
Included observations: 34				
Sources of Causation	Dependent variables			
	D(LSJH)	D(LHRS)	D(LINT)	D(LUNEMP)
D(LSJH)		4.064062 (0.0438)	7.94253 (0.0048)	2.379259 (0.123)
D(LHRS)	0.994217 (0.3187)		0.033575 (0.8546)	1.373968 (0.2411)
D(LINT)	4.645620 (0.0311)	0.50588 (0.4769)		3.870555 (0.0491)
D(LUNEMP)	0.279231 (0.5972)	5.223999 (0.0223)	0.001689 (0.9672)	
ALL	6.361979 (0.0953)	7.422686 (0.0596)	9.501901 (0.0233)	6.222459 (0.1013)

() denotes the p value

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

The VECM Granger Causality Test is presented in Table – 9. This table confirms that in the short run the liquidity constraint (LINT) Granger causes second job holding in Lithuania at 5% level of significance. The hours constraint (LHRS) and the unemployment rate (LUNEMP) failed to Granger cause second job holding in Lithuania at 5% level of significance. Long run causality running from hours constraint (LHRS), liquidity constraint (LINT) and unemployment rate (LUNEMP) to the second job holding in Lithuania (LSJH) is confirmed through the VECM analysis. However, VECM Granger Causality Test confirms that, except for the liquidity constraint (LINT), no such causality from the hours constraint (LHRS) and the unemployment rate (LUNEMP) to the second job holding in Lithuania occurs in the short run.

5

Conclusion

According to the research on economics of second job holding, the most important factor determining the second job holding is the ‘hours constraint’. It is the workers’ inability to supply as many work hours as they wish at their utility-maximizing level. Shisko and Rostker (1976) developed a solid microeconomic foundation for the hypothesized link between second job keeping and hours constraint. Prospective cross-sectional and panel studies have confirmed the effect of the ‘hours constraints’ on second job holding. These findings prompted us to study

the long run relationship between second job holding and hours constraint in Lithuania. Liquidity constraint, the limited availability of liquid funds, has also been identified as a key factor influencing second job holding by Abdukadir (1992). Since interest rate is directly linked with money supply, quarterly money market interest rate is considered as a proxy for liquidity constraint in this study.

Relation between multiple jobholding and unemployment was first anticipated by Coghill (1967). The prospective studies also confirm the relationship between unemployment and second job holding (e.g., Frey and Schneider (2000), Amuedo-Dorantes and Kimmel (2005), Robinson (2009), Panos, Pouliakas and Zangelidis (2011), Zangelidis (2014)). Therefore, we have considered unemployment as a key factor of second job holding. The purpose of this paper is to highlight the significance of key factors like the hours constraint, liquidity constraint and the unemployment rate in influencing second job holding in Lithuania through VECM analysis using Eurostat data for the period of 2005 Q1 to 2013 Q4.

Since application of ADF and PP tests verify that all the variables are $I(1)$, the Johansen Cointegration test has been conducted to investigate the long-run association between second job holding, hours constraint, liquidity constraint (or quarterly interest rate) and unemployment in Lithuania. Both the Trace and Maximum Eigenvalue tests has confirmed that there are two cointegrating equation. This implies that in Lithuania, there is equilibrium relationship between second job holding (LSJH), hours constraint (LHRS), interest rate (LINT) and unemployment (LUNEMP) in the long run. Since cointegration vectors exist, VECM analysis has been conducted using Eurostat data for the period of 2005 Q1 to 2013 Q4 in order to investigate the dynamic behavior of the variables.

The corresponding error correction coefficient in VECM analysis is found to be significant and has a negative sign. This finding confirms that there is a long run causality running from hours constraint (LHRS), interest rate (LINT) and unemployment (LUNEMP) to second job holding (LSJH) in Lithuania. However no short-run causality from LHRS and LUNEMP to LSJH has been identified. The VECM Granger Causality Test also supports the fact that except interest rate (LINT), the hours constraint and unemployment rate do not Granger cause second job holding (LSJH) in Lithuania.

Therefore, it is concluded that second job holding in the long run in Lithuania is a result of hours constraint, money or liquidity constraint and unemployment rate. The FMOLS estimates of cointegration relationship suggest that likelihood of second job holding decreases due to hours constraint, interest rate and unemployment rate. But unlike interest rate, unemployment rate or hours constraint cannot be blamed for influencing second job holding in Lithuania in the short run.

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